

Realistic 3D Skin Modeling for Microwave Detection of Basal Cell Carcinoma

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Abstract— Microwave and millimeter-wave techniques are promising for non-invasive skin cancer detection due to their sensitivity to tissue dielectric properties. In this study, realistic three-dimensional (3D) skin models, including nodular basal cell carcinoma (BCC), are generated by combining Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and ultrasound (US) imaging. These models are used in finite-difference time-domain electromagnetic simulations to evaluate the power reflection coefficient over the 10–100 GHz frequency range.

The results show a consistently higher reflection from skin containing BCC compared to healthy skin, particularly at frequencies above 20 GHz. This behaviour is attributed to the increased permittivity associated with the higher free water content of BCC tissue. Additional simulations with increased permittivity values further demonstrate the sensitivity of the reflected power to water content variations. These findings support the potential of microwave-based techniques for non-invasive detection of skin cancer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Basal cell carcinoma (BCC) is the most common type of skin cancer, and its early detection is essential for effective treatment. Conventional diagnostic approaches often rely on visual inspection and invasive biopsies, motivating the development of non-invasive techniques that provide quantitative tissue characterization.

Microwave and millimeter-wave methods are promising for skin cancer detection due to their sensitivity to tissue dielectric properties, which are strongly influenced by water content. Malignant skin tissues such as BCC exhibit higher free water content than healthy skin, leading to increased permittivity and conductivity and, consequently, to measurable changes in reflected electromagnetic signals.

In this work, we present a framework for generating realistic three-dimensional skin models by combining Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and ultrasound (US) imaging. These models are employed in electromagnetic simulations to study the reflection characteristics of healthy skin and nodular BCC over the 10–100 GHz frequency range, highlighting the potential of microwave techniques for non-invasive skin cancer detection.

II. 3D SKIN MODEL CONSTRUCTION

We have applied a framework that aims to generate realistic 3D skin models by combining complementary imaging modalities and structured data processing. It follows three main stages: image acquisition, image processing, and data synthesis.

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and ultrasound (US) imaging are jointly used to capture information from both superficial and deeper skin layers, leveraging the strengths of each modality.

During the image acquisition stage, OCT and US scans are obtained from the target skin region. OCT data are primarily used to characterize superficial skin layers, while US data provide information on deeper tissue thicknesses. The image processing stage focuses on segmentation and measurement. From the OCT images, key anatomical interfaces within the superficial skin are identified and segmented, including the boundaries between the stratum corneum, viable epidermis, nodular BCC region and dermis. These segmented interfaces from consecutive OCT images are combined to reconstruct corresponding three-dimensional surfaces at a resolution of $5 \mu\text{m} \times 50 \mu\text{m} \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ ($x \times y \times z$; Fig. 1).

US imaging is incorporated in the framework to measure the thickness of deeper tissue layers, such as the dermis and subcutaneous fat, which cannot be reliably segmented in OCT images. Due to the limited spatial resolution of US (0.1mm) for fine structural reconstruction, these deeper interfaces are generally modeled as planar surfaces.

In the final data synthesis stage, the segmented OCT-derived surfaces and US-based measurements are integrated to construct the complete 3D skin model. The processed data are imported into Sim4Life (ZMT, Switzerland) software, where computer-aided design tools are used to assemble the layered geometry and generate the final realistic 3D representation of the skin (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Overview of the 3D skin modeling workflow, including (a) OCT and US image acquisition, (b) OCT segmentation and US-based depth measurements of key tissue interfaces, and (c) data integration and 3D model construction.

III. EM MODELLING AND SIMULATION

In addition to the geometric model, electromagnetic simulations require the specification of the dielectric properties—namely permittivity and electrical conductivity—of

the constituent materials (skin and subcutaneous layers). Accordingly, the permittivity and electrical conductivity of the Stratum Corneum (SC), Viable Epidermis (VE), Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC), Dermis (DE), Fat (FT), and Muscle (MS) layers must be defined. The frequency dependent dielectric properties reported in [1] were applied to the SC, FT, and MS layers. Values from [2] were used for the VE and DE skin layers, while the dielectric properties of the “Malignant BCC” group reported in [3] were applied to the BCC region of the model.

The electromagnetic (EM) simulation was conducted using the Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) method implemented in the Sim4Life software platform. A linearly polarized plane-wave source with a power density of 1 W/m², propagating along an axis perpendicular to the skin layers, was employed. A uniform grid with a resolution of 20 μm was applied. This grid size is sufficiently small to satisfy the λ/10 rule of thumb for the shortest wavelength (≈ 1 mm in the MS layer at 100 GHz) and to capture the anatomical details of the 3D model, while remaining large enough to avoid entering the cellular scale, which would require a different modeling approach. Perfect Electric Conductors (PECs) and Perfect Magnetic Conductors (PMCs) were applied to the sides of the computational domain, perpendicular to the E and H fields, respectively, while Perfectly Matched Layers (PMLs) were applied at the top and bottom. This setup effectively simulates an infinitely repeating geometry of the 3D model by mirroring it along the four lateral sides. A horizontal plane placed above the air–skin interface, within the scattered-field region, was used to evaluate the power flux density in order to determine the power reflection coefficient over the 10–100 GHz frequency range.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two different 3D models were simulated: (a) one including nodular BCC tissue (labeled “BCC”) and (b) one without BCC tissue (labeled “healthy skin”). In case (b), the BCC tissue was replaced with VE tissue while maintaining the same geometry. The power reflection coefficient as evaluated from simulated results for the two different models over the 10–100 GHz frequency range are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Power reflection coefficient for healthy skin (orange) and skin with nodular basal cell carcinoma (blue), evaluated over the 10–100 GHz frequency range using 3D skin modeling.

Higher reflection is observed at frequencies above 20 GHz, highlighting the potential of microwave techniques for skin cancer detection. This behavior can be attributed to the higher free (bulk) water content of BCC tissue (~15%). Measurement results from BCC skin samples [3] show an approximately 10% increase in both the real and imaginary parts of the complex permittivity (ϵ) of an equivalent skin tissue representing the BCC condition. Applying a 10% increase in ϵ over the examined frequency range yields differences in the power reflection coefficient that are in good agreement with the simulated values shown in Figure 3 (blue line).

Two additional cases with higher complex permittivity values (increased by 10% and 20% compared to [3], corresponding to higher free water content) were also simulated for the BCC tissue to highlight the impact of water content on the reflected power.

Future work includes realistic 3D modelling of different BCC cases (e.g., varying thicknesses and shapes), as well as other skin conditions (e.g., squamous cell carcinoma), and the study of their corresponding behaviour in the context of microwave imaging techniques.

Figure 3. Power reflection coefficient difference between healthy skin and skin with BCC (blue), including cases with higher considered complex permittivity by 10% (orange) and 20% (green).

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